

ISic2954

I.Sicily inscription 2954

Language

Sikel

Type

votive (?)

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Morgantina

Place of origin (modern)

Morgantina

Provenance

Archaic settlement

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Aidone, Museo Archeologico di
Aidone, inventory 61-1258

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336164

1. [—]YPIEIAI P [. .] I [—]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645319

PHI 336164

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 49.1310

Antonaccio, C. M. 1999. An inscribed stele from archaic Morgantina. *Kadmos*. 38: 87-96.

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2954. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387793>